

IDEA - Integrating Diversity into the Evaluation and Assessment of Researchers

Action plan for the Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam

Version 2

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List of contributors (i.e. co-creators) to be added

1. Background and methodology

Diversity, equity and inclusion (DEI) in the research workforce are essential to conduct good quality research which is of societal relevance. It can also help to address known biases in research outputs, such as gender and racial bias. There are different factors that influence DEI in research institutions, including 1) hiring, 2) researcher evaluations and rewards, as well as 3) working practices themselves. At the VU, the Diversity Office has implemented a Colorful Staff Action plan that addresses these three elements. However, so far, only the first two elements have been directly addressed, and researcher evaluations and rewards have not yet been directly targeted with a focus on DEI.

At the same time, in the context of the national Recognition and Rewards (R&R) program, there are ongoing researcher evaluation reforms taking place at the VU. The focus of these is to shift away from perverse incentives in research which reward a high number of high impact publications, to promote fairer, quality research, education and leadership practices instead. The central VU R&R program was published last year, and in the past months, all faculties have translated these into more detailed and concrete faculty policies which include detailed evaluation criteria for Assistant, Associate, and Full Professors. However, so far, there has been little focus within these efforts on DEI.

Therefore, in the IDEA project running from January-December 2025, funded by the CoARA Boost Programme, we aimed to create an action plan for the VU on how to integrate DEI considerations into the ongoing reforms regarding researcher evaluations. We used a generative design methodology to conduct 4 co-creation workshops to develop the action plan. Workshop 1 consisted of 8 recognition and rewards (R&R) experts at the VU, while workshops 2, 3 and 4 included 27, 9, and 8 DEI and R&R experts in the Netherlands and beyond, respectively. The workshops were informed by a state of the art literature review on DEI in researcher evaluations ([link](#)), as well as an analysis of faculty policies ([link](#)). The action plan below consists of a set of recommendations developed with the co-creators. Important to note is that the action plan addresses academic researchers at the VU, rather than all staff, due to practical reasons, including the fact that the R&R program itself is only focused on this target group.

2. Action plan

Recommendation 1: Prioritize and integrate DEI considerations into R&R policy revisions and implementation at the central, faculty and department levels.

Our analysis of current faculty policies shows that only one of the faculties (BETA) has actually addressed DEI concerns explicitly in its policy on R&R. However, there can be no ‘fair’ evaluation without addressing questions related to DEI. Therefore, we see **the neglect of DEI in current R&R efforts at the VU as a big blind spot** that needs to be addressed. The VU prides itself as being a diverse university, with a diverse student population and many initiatives focused on fostering equity and inclusion. Yet, to ensure that this pride is based on more than just optics, it is necessary that DEI is also deeply rooted in the university’s policies. R&R policies are particularly important because diversity is strongly impacted by how researcher evaluations are performed (see our [map](#) of critical points for diversity along academic career trajectories). As a starting point, both the central policy and other faculties can look to the BETA R&R policy as a baseline for the meaningful integration of DEI considerations.

From our co-creative work, we have learned that especially at higher academic ranks - which are the ones targeted by R&R - there is a tendency to reduce DEI to binary understandings of gender equality. We strongly urge the VU to reject this approach and not just focus on hiring and promoting more women researchers. Instead, we advise the VU to rather **take an intersectional approach to DEI which considers different dimensions of marginalisation** (including gender as a spectrum, LGBTQI+ identities, racialization, religious minorities, ethnicity, disabilities, neurodivergence, and difference in socio-economic resources) **as well as their intersections**. Furthermore, to truly foster DEI, it is necessary to focus on equity rather than equality. In practice this means that instead of finding ways to provide equal opportunities, the VU should ensure that the necessary accommodations are taken into account for researchers’ differing needs. For instance, it might be that someone with certain disabilities or care-taking responsibilities will not be able to participate in the expected number of academic activities because of their situation; rather than penalizing, this should be accounted for in promotion processes.

To ensure that both those on evaluation committees and candidates are aware about the DEI dimensions of the R&R policies, it is important to **make the DEI aspects highly visible within the policy**. This could be realized, for instance, through the use of a roadmap for researchers on what kind of support is available to address their unique needs and how they can access and make use of it. For this, collaboration with grass-roots and bottom up DEI initiatives at the level of departments or university wide networks is necessary.

Recommendation 2: Monitor and document the state of DEI at the university.

Taking DEI seriously also requires understanding the challenges and gaps regarding DEI at the institution. For this, it is necessary to **collect data about researcher demographics across career stages** at the institution. Without keeping track of researcher demographics, it is difficult to know what to strive for in terms of promoting DEI through evaluation and promotions and to track progress. While the GDPR poses some concerns that need to be addressed for such data

collection, it does not prevent the data collection from taking place but requires considering how to do so in an ethical and robust way. This aligns with the [National Action Plan for Greater Diversity and Inclusion in Higher Education and Research \(2020\)](#), which identifies as one of its goals finding ways to monitor diversity and inclusion on a structural basis in the context of research and higher education.

Another way to keep track of the state of DEI at the VU is to **keep an overview of resistant parties' concerns regarding DEI**, and try to address those via different methods. For instance, many stakeholders might assume that DEI leads to less meritocracy and quality, but evidence shows that this is not true, and that DEI instead leads to better quality work. Communicating this in events and policy clearly could help to address such unsubstantiated concerns.

Recommendation 3: Address how to conduct fair and unbiased recruitment and promotion procedures as part of the R&R policy.

Currently, the R&R central and faculty policies focus on the promotion criteria that faculty are assessed on. However, ensuring fair promotion and recognition requires more than just shifting away from criteria that focus on quantity to ones that address quality. Fair recognition and rewards also requires that the procedures used to recruit and evaluate researchers are fair and unbiased. This involves several considerations:

- **The composition of recruitment and promotion committees:** Considering the phenomenon of implicit biases, some diversity in committees themselves is necessary to foster DEI. Although it might be difficult to ensure intersectional diversity due to practicalities (e.g. of higher academic positions lacking a diverse workforce), at least diversity in research positions, ranks, and gender could be taken into account here. This is particularly important if it is clearly known that there are imbalances (e.g. regarding gender) in a specific faculty or department. The composition of recruitment and promotion committees is important both directly and indirectly: directly because it addresses (implicit) biases, and indirectly because it prevents the situation where candidates do not see themselves as suiting the department or faculty themselves (e.g. if the candidate is a woman of color being interviewed by all white men).
- **Training of recruitment and promotion committees:** Our conversations with HR and diversity experts in the workshops showed us that recruitment and promotion procedures in the university often fall short of best practice standards known by HR and diversity experts. For instance, committee members lack knowledge about what questions they are allowed to ask candidates, how to identify and handle conflicts of interest, and how to ensure fairness and reduce bias through the recruitment and promotion process. Therefore, it is essential that all members of recruitment and promotion committees undergo training on these topics before they meet with candidates and are tasked with deliberations and decision making. To support this training, it could also be helpful for the VU to provide easy to read, short guidance documents to committee members.

- **Preventing and handling conflicts of interest:** In our workshops, we discussed how it is not uncommon for candidates to be assessed by colleagues, fellow department members, and even supervisors. Yet, this type of practice prevents an unbiased promotion procedure and constitutes a conflict of interest. Therefore, we strongly urge the VU to provide clear guidance to promotion committees on how to identify and handle such conflicts of interest.
- **Conducting unbiased procedures:** There are certain best practices for unbiased recruitment and evaluation procedures, which we believe the VU should promote and ensure. These involve asking candidates a standard set of questions, giving every candidate a fair chance to respond, and preventing irrelevant third-party information from biasing the selection and promotion process.
- **Involving HR:** Considering that researchers are already over-tasked in the university, even with guidance and training, it is not reasonable to expect that they have the most up-to-date and complete information about fair recruitment and promotion. Therefore, all recruitment and promotion processes should be guided and led actively by HR staff. HR should be responsible to ensure, for instance, that researchers take into account contextual factors that might influence different candidates' CVs. For example, HR can provide guidance on how conference attendances should be interpreted in light of unfair visa regulations across the world preventing candidates from certain nationalities from joining events abroad.

The involvement of HR is crucial since biased decision making is very subtle. For instance, sometimes a candidate is not selected because of reasons such as 'I don't think that this person fits in the team'. If HR is trained to push back in these kinds of situations to ask: 'That's not concrete enough, what do you expect and what is missing?', that could really help to prevent even subtle biases (e.g. where people exclude others because they do not look or act like them) and lead to more fair recruitment and evaluation.

Recommendation 4: Involve the central R&R team more in the R&R practices and developments within the faculties.

Based on our workshops, our understanding is that the R&R policies are currently being implemented in a very decentralized way. Although it is beneficial to allow faculties flexibility in adapting R&R to fit their needs, too much decentralization prevents faculties from learning from each other and meeting core requirements (e.g. related to addressing DEI or other topics important for R&R, such as open science). Furthermore, it can create a lack of transparency on the state of R&R developments at the university, and create undesirable differences between faculties and departments. Therefore, we recommend **regular communication moments between the central R&R team and the faculties** to ensure an exchange of knowledge and practices on R&R, as well as continuous monitoring, improvement and learning from each other. This communication **should be formally led by a dedicated central policy advisor**.

Additionally, **having set people within each faculty who report to each other and are responsible for the policies** is vital to ensuring that accountability for implementation is considered, which is necessary for bringing real change. Furthermore, specific key performance indicators or drivers should be used to monitor R&R implementation. These indicators and drivers should focus not just on promotions - since R&R is more than just focused on the final results of who is promoted - but also involve research culture and work environment indicators.

Recommendation 5: Explicate how care-taking and leaves affects researcher recruitment and promotion, implementing equity focused policies on this.

Our faculty policy analysis shows that only three faculty provide any considerations of care-taking roles and leaves of researchers (BETA, ACTA, and SBE), for instance related to having and taking care of children, taking care of others (e.g. older parents), or taking sick, or transition leaves. Even within these faculties, there is not much concrete explanation about how these situations should be handled within recruitment and promotions. One reason for this is the thought that culture, rather than policy, needs to change in order to more fairly recognize and reward those with care-taking responsibilities or needs for sick leaves. However, throughout our workshops, we have discussed that culture will not change on its own and needs a policy push. Therefore, our advice is to address the following points:

- **More clear guidance about how to assess those with care-obligations, parental leaves, and transition and sick leaves**, for instance by not penalizing them but being even more appreciative of what they are able to achieve within the time that they are able to commit to their academic work.
- Researchers should have **access to information about their legal and institutional rights regarding leaves and care-taking**, as well as the procedures, services and support mechanisms available in cases where these rights are not respected. For instance, lactating parents should be informed of their right to be compensated for breast-feeding or making use of lactation rooms during working hours. Furthermore, guidance to institutional facilities should be provided. All of this should be accounted for when it comes to evaluation (e.g. related to expectations of the number of achievements that can be reached when being a lactating parent).
- In line with best practices in other institutions, faculties could look into the possibility to **provide funds to support researchers re-integrating in the work-force after leave**.
- The university as a whole could consider providing **financial compensation to departments** who hire staff that cannot dedicate 1FTE for their academic work.

Implementation of this recommendation requires excellent communication between HR and management and employees, and that research managers are trained in how to effectively communicate these topics to their academic staff (e.g. using respectful language). Furthermore,

collaboration with specific networks representing marginalized groups (e.g. the LGBTQI+ network) could also help to communicate rights to researchers.

Recommendation 6: Incorporate policies for fair R&R also at earlier levels of research, including students, PhD candidates and postdocs.

DEI concerns influencing the research workforce start much earlier than the Assistant Professor position, since there are already a lot of selection factors that are biased against certain marginalized groups at the student, PhD and postdoc level (see our [map](#) of critical points for diversity along academic career trajectories). PhD candidates and postdocs are some of the most vulnerable research members, because of their position in research and precarity in contracts. Therefore, it is crucial that **students, research assistants, PhD candidates and postdocs are also addressed by R&R policies**. This does not necessarily have to entail expanding the current R&R framework at the VU to take into account PhD candidates and postdocs, but there should at least be attention from somewhere about how to recruit and promote fairly, focusing on quality rather than quantity, also at these levels. This is especially necessary for the DEI dimension, considering that there is much more diversity in student, PhD candidates and postdocs (and students) at the VU, compared to higher academic ranks. To promote DEI beyond these levels, there should be sufficient **attention from the VU on how to promote more diverse bodies from these lower academic ranks**. Most likely a collaboration between policy teams for students, HR and the central Diversity team on developing policy and action on this point would be ideal in addressing these groups. Different approaches that could help here include:

- Universities can participate in **career days and fairs** focusing on **targeting diverse students** with the goal of showing that the university is itself a career destination.
- **Information on drop-outs** from the bachelor to master level, and master to PhD level should be collected to understand how to reduce drop-outs and increase retention.
- Adding a blurb to all vacancies, particularly for junior and PhD positions to **encourage students from diverse backgrounds to apply even if they do not formally meet all the vacancy criteria**, could encourage those that doubt themselves to apply.
- Focus on how to give some stability to those in junior positions through **reducing short term and temporary contracts**, since people without resources are less able to navigate unstable positions and are more likely to leave academia.

Recommendation 7: Implement inclusive leadership.

Many grass-roots and bottom up initiatives related to DEI exist at the VU. However, to have the most impact, there is a need for top-down support and prioritization of DEI efforts. This requires inclusive leadership. Inclusive leadership means more than just considering the number of women in leadership positions. Inclusive leadership means that all research leaders, including principle investigators, research chairs, department heads, and faculty boards are both DEI literate and committed to DEI.

This requires **ensuring that research leaders undergo DEI training** (e.g. on unconscious bias, bystander training, social safety, inclusive leadership), also covering the researcher evaluation aspect, and that there are **clear leadership frameworks** that set forth expectations about research leaders on how they lead inclusively and foster DEI within their sphere of influence. Such training and even the monitoring of inclusive leadership and other DEI factors could also be conducted by external parties to ensure independence and specialized expertise. A culture of accountability, where there is zero tolerance towards misbehaviors exists, should be stimulated through these means.

Furthermore, it is helpful if **inclusive leadership is itself a formal evaluation criterion** for the promotion of research leaders (including e.g. professors), or also as part of the 'leadership' component in earlier stages of promotion. It is also beneficial if supervisors' supervisors or leaders' supervisors address inclusive leadership in meetings and evaluation moments with their supervisee. Finally, 360 feedback mechanisms, where not only peers and supervisors, but also PhD candidates and other professional staff members are asked to provide input to leaders, is important in integrating inclusivity in leadership assessment processes.

Of course, inclusive leadership should ideally also reflect more diversity within leadership positions within the VU, taking into account not just binary notions of gender, but also race, ethnicity, religion, socio-economic origins, ability, LGBTQI identity, and religion. This entire action plan attempts to contribute to that aim, but the aim will need time and institutional commitment to be realized.

Recommendation 8: Recognize and reward DEI-related work and other forms of invisible labor.

Based on our literature review and workshops, we see that much of the work related to DEI is carried out on a voluntary basis, often outside of working hours and without formal recognition or compensation. This situation contributes to what has been described as *invisible labor*: a form of emotional, relational, and service work that is undervalued within academic reward systems. The disproportionate burden of such labor often falls on those from underrepresented or marginalized groups. To address this imbalance, specific time and financial resources should be allocated for this work, ensuring that those engaged in advancing DEI do not do so at the expense of their research productivity or career progression. Moreover, faculty policies should explicitly acknowledge DEI-related work and other forms of currently invisible labor, such as mentoring and community-building, as part of formal academic labor that can be recognized and rewarded in hiring, evaluation, and promotion processes. To frame this recommendation more concretely, we highly advise the VU faculties to **formally incorporate different forms of DEI work as part of the evaluation criteria** that researchers are assessed on.